

Effects of Physical Properties of Some Papers on Offset Printing Quality

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Abstract

The aim of the study was to determine the effects of the physical properties of some papers on the offset printing quality. For this purpose, the physical properties of 230 and 350 gsm American Bristol cardboard, 115 gsm Matt and Gloss Coated Paper, 70 and 80 gsm I. high grade paper, 48 and 54 gsm II. medium grade paper, 70 and 80 gsm III. low grade paper which are commonly used in offset printing were experimentally examined in accordance with relevant standards. The papers were printed with offset printing techniques and qualities of the printings were measured via the print control strips. Then, the obtained results were assessed in accordance with ISO 12647-2 quality standard. The results indicated that the increased grammage, bulkiness, thickness, and air permeability led to improvements in dot gain, print contrasts, and trapping values, but caused reduced print density. The tensile, burst and tear strengths have no significant effects on printing qualities.

Keywords: Physical Properties, Offset, Printing Quality

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1. Bazı Kağıtların Fiziksel Özelliklerinin Offset Baskı Kalitesi Üzerine Etkileri

Özet

Bu çalışmada, bazı kağıtların fiziksel özelliklerinin offset baskı kalitesi üzerine etkilerinin belirlenmesini amaçlanmıştır. Bu amaçla, offset baskıda yaygın bir şekilde kullanılan 230 ve 350 gsm Amerikan Bristol, 115 gsm mat ve parlak kuşeli kağıt, 70 ve 870 gsm I. sınıf, 48 ve 54 gsm II. sınıf 70 ve 80 gsm III. sınıf kağıtlar ilgili standartlara bağlı kalınarak offset baskıda kullanılmıştır. Offset baskı yapılan bu kağıtların baskı kaliteleri baskı kontrol şeritleri yardımıyla ölçülmüştür. Elde edilen sonuçlar ISO 12647-2 kalite standardına göre değerlendirilmiştir. Elde edilen sonuçlara göre gramaj, kalınlık, hacimlilik ve hava geçirgenliği değerleri arttıkça nokta kazancı, baskı kontrastı ve trapping değerleri iyileşmiş, baskı yoğunluğu ise azalmıştır. Kopma, patlama ve yırtılma mukavemetlerinin ise baskı kalitesi üzerine etkisinin olmadığı tespit edilmiştir.

Anahtar Kelimeler: Fiziksel Özellikler, Offset, Baskı Kalitesi

INTRODUCTION

Offset printing system invented even after other printing system is still the most preferred printing system today. The advantages in harmonization of the offset printing system in this regard are the most important factors. Using computer aided technologies improves the quality, prevents loss time, and provides versatile savings. Offset printing technology used for copy of quality products such

as newspapers, magazines, and brochure has gradually become a part of the cardboard packaging industry. Offset printing is a widely used printing system because it is easy to use and provides a good quality of printing (Sahin et al., 2013).

In terms of surface properties and production methods, papers have different properties. While cellulose content in some paper production is high, some paper surfaces are processed or fillers are added into them. All these differences make up different paper properties such as glossy, matte, rough, satin, thick, thin, opaque, transparent. Papers and cardboards that have significant impact on the printing process and finish are important for print compliance (Aydemir, 2014).

It is possible to make print measurements with different measuring devices in offset printing technique. CMYK color values can be measured with densitometer or spectrophotometer, which has the ability to measure the densitometric measurement. It is necessary to use the print control strips (Fig 1) during printing in order to measure with these devices. There are special zones on the print control strips for measuring dot gain, print density and trapping values. Printing quality can be controlled with evaluating measurements on these zones. The standardization code developed by ISO for offset printing technology in the printing industry is code 12647-2 (Sahin, 2012).

Figure 1. Print control strip

Dot gain is a phenomenon in offset lithography and some other forms of printing which causes printed material to look darker than intended (Johansson et al., 2012). Trapping value is the ability of a printed ink to accept the next printed ink compared to how well paper accepts that ink (Borojevic et al., 2014). The print density indicates how much ink is on the layer. In order to measure the ink density and determine each CMYK colors, 100% layer must be formed on the edge of the papers to be printed. The print contrast is a method of evaluating and optimizing the density of the ink deposited on the substrate during printing (Adamcewicz, 1994).

Color gamut is the color pallet that a given technology or process is capable of reproducing. In order to understand gamut, it is important to understand the CIE diagram (Fig 2). It is the result of extensive research about human vision (Stone et al., 1988).

Figure 2 - CIE diagram

The chroma means "color saturation" and can be measured by color intensity. It is desirable that the color saturation, which is the decisive factor for a good print quality, is high (Sonmez, 2011).

The chrome value is calculated according to the following formula:

$$C = \sqrt{a^2 + b^2} \quad (1)$$

C: Chroma

a : The red-green colors of the print

b : The yellow-blue colors of the print

Used in a wide variety of forms, paper and paperboard are characterized by a wide range of properties. In the thousands of paper varieties available, some properties differ only slightly and others grossly. The identification and expression of these differences depend upon the application of standard test methods, generally specified by industry and engineering associations in the papermaking countries of the world. Weight or substance per unit area, called basis weight, is a fundamental property of paper and paperboard products (ISO, 2012). The caliper (thickness) of paper or paperboard in fractions of a millimeter or inch is measured by placing a single sheet (Hu et al., 2013). The density or specific gravity of paper is calculated from the basis weight and thickness, and may vary over wide limits (ISO, 2011). Tensile strength is the maximum tensile force developed in a test specimen before rupture on a tensile test carried to rupture under prescribed conditions. Tensile strength (as used here) is the force per unit width of test specimen (TAPPI, 2013). One of the oldest and most widely used strength tests for paper and paperboard is the bursting test, or Mullen test. It is defined as the hydrostatic pressure (caused by liquids at rest) necessary to cause rupture in a circular area of a given diameter. Other strength test for which standard methods exist is tearing strength (TAPPI, 2015).

The main material of the offset printing system is paper as well as the other printing systems. It is predicted that the different physical properties of the papers will be different in offset printing quality measurement parameters. In this study, offset printing techniques were applied to the papers with different physical properties. Qualities of the printings were measured via the print control strips.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

This study was performed at the Kahramanmaras Sutcu Imam University, Faculty of Forestry, Pulp and Paper Production Laboratory. The test papers were conditioned at 23 ± 1 °C and 65% relative humidity in conditioning room accordance with TAPPI T 402 om-88 standard. Then, they were prepared for the physical tests. Tests were performed according to the standards given in Table 1.

After the physical properties were determined, offset printing of the samples was carried out by the printing machine Heidelberg Speedmaster CD 102. 500 prints were applied to each sample. A total of 3 samples were taken from the 100th prints, 300th prints, and 500th prints.

Table 2. Applied tests on the papers and standards (Anon., 1998)

Physical Properties	Standards
Grammage	TAPPI T 410 om-88
Thickness	TAPPI T 411 om-89
Density and Bulkiness	TAPPI T 411 om-89
Tensile Strengths	TAPPI T 494 om-01
Tear Strengths	TAPPI T 414 om-88
Burst Strengths	TAPPI T 403 om-91
Surface Roughness	TAPPI T 575 om-07
Air Permeability	TAPPI T 460 om-02

The printing qualities of the paper samples such as print contrast, print density, dot gain, gamut, chroma and L, a, b values were determined by using Exact Densitometer and Mean values were calculated with the values of each three samples. These printing qualities were applied according to the ISO 12647-2 standard.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The physical properties of each paper were presented in Table 2. In consideration of these physical properties, offset printing was performed in the 80 and 40 tram area and dot gains of CMYK colors were measured according to ISO 12647-2 standard and given in Table 3. In Table 4, findings of the print density and print contrast values of the offset printed papers were shown. The trapping values of the papers were presented in Table 5. The gamut values of the printed papers were given in Table 6. Lastly, the chroma, L, a, and b values of the offset printed papers were presented in Tables 7 and 8.

Table 3. The physical properties of each paper

Physical Properties	American Bristol		Coated (115 gsm)		I. High Grade		II. Medium Grade		III. Low Grade	
	230 gsm	350 gsm	Matt	Gloss	70 gsm	80 gsm	48 gsm	54 gsm	70 gsm	80 gsm
Grammage (g/m ²) (gsm)	224	342	115	115	70	78	49	54	71	81
Breaking Length (CD)	3.2	2.5	2.6	1.2	2.0	1.8	1.9	1.4	1.3	2.4
Breaking Length (MD) (km)	5.7	4.7	3.9	4.6	4.6	4.5	4.0	3.9	3.5	4.5
Burst Index (kPa m ² /g)	2.82	2.40	2.05	2.09	2.26	2.20	1.60	1.18	1.24	2.31
Tear Index (mN.m ² .g)	5.07	4.82	4.09	4.02	4.51	3.95	3.99	3.25	6.05	5.11
Bulkiness (cm ³ /g)	1.34	1.39	0.18	0.94	1.22	1.28	1.52	1.54	1.69	1.06
Density (g/cm ³)	0.75	0.72	1.28	1.06	0.82	0.79	0.66	0.65	0.59	0.95
Thickness (Micron)	300	475	90	110	85	100	75	83	120	85
Air Permeability (m ³ /min)	-	-	-	-	519	688	109	120	294	132
Surface Roughness (ml/min)	2.4	170	0-3	5	302	366	75	104	103	339

In Table 3, it was observed that the papers with high values grammage have high dot gain values. When Tables 2 and 3 were examined, increases in the density, tensile, burst, and tear strengths have negative effect on the dot gain values. Besides, when the thickness, air permeability, and bulkiness values increased, increases in dot gain have been observed. The dot gain values were not changed in both coated papers (Matt and Gloss). When all the papers were compared in terms of dot gain values, it was determined that the most suitable papers were I. High Grade papers with 70 and 80 gsm.

Table 4. The dot gains of the offset printed papers

Tram Area	American Bristol				Coated (115 gsm)				I. High Grade			
	230 gsm		350 gsm		Matt		Gloss		70 gsm		80 gsm	
	80	40	80	40	80	40	80	40	80	40	80	40
Cyan (C)	16.8	20.2	17.2	24.4	16.2	26.5	16.3	26.6	13.6	20.2	14.2	21.4
Magenta (M)	13.2	21.2	13.7	21.3	14	20.9	14.4	21.7	12.6	20.8	13.5	21.7
Yellow (Y)	14.9	29.4	15.4	30.1	15	19.7	15.2	20.1	12.5	19.7	13.1	22.5
Key (K)	8.2	14.1	9.2	15.4	8.6	13.8	9.2	14	12.6	23.4	13.6	24.7
	II. Medium Grade				III. Low Grade							
	48 gsm		54 gsm		70 gsm		80 gsm					
Tram Area	80	40	80	40	80	40	80	40				
Cyan (C)	16.6	22.3	15.6	21.9	15.3	27.1	16.2	28.2				
Magenta (M)	16.2	23.5	15.8	22.1	13.9	23.2	13.9	23.2				
Yellow (Y)	15.5	23.7	15.4	22.4	14.6	26.4	15.8	29.3				
Key (K)	14.9	28.7	13.6	27.7	12.7	23.7	13.7	25.5				

In Table 4, it was observed that the increases in the grammages decreased the print density values and did not affect the print contrast. According to the results of Tables 2 and 4, increases the bulkiness, thickness, and air permeability values decreased the print density values, increased the print contrast. With increasing in the tensile, tear, and burst strengths, the print density values decreased and the print contrast increased. There was no significant difference between the matt and gloss coated paper in terms of the print density and print contrast values. III. Low Grade papers gave the best result in the print density values.

Table 5. The print density and print contrasts of the offset printed papers

	American Bristol				Coated (115 gsm)				I. High Grade			
	230 gsm		350 gsm		Matt		Gloss		70 gsm		80 gsm	
	D	C	D	C	D	C	D	C	D	C	D	C
	Cyan (C)	1.64	29.1	1.56	30.4	1.66	31.2	1.66	30.8	1.31	24.6	1.17
Magenta (M)	1.37	33	1.30	33.7	1.31	31.7	1.34	30.9	1.12	23.5	1.05	25.5
Yellow (Y)	1.33	23.8	1.29	24.8	1.21	27.3	1.30	25.3	1.19	23	1.15	24.4
Key (K)	1.58	41.9	1.56	47.9	1.50	50.9	1.52	49.9	1.47	39.6	1.42	40.9

	II. Medium Grade				III. Low Grade			
	48 gsm		54 gsm		70 gsm		80 gsm	
	D	C	D	C	D	C	D	C
	Cyan (C)	1.30	21.3	1.35	20.6	1.16	24.3	1.23
Magenta (M)	1.14	21.7	1.15	20.9	1.00	25.4	1.00	25.1
Yellow (Y)	1.12	21.3	1.15	19.7	0.98	21.5	1.06	18
Key (K)	1.22	30.5	1.25	28.3	1.21	37.6	1.34	33.7

* D refers to print density, C refers to print contrast

In Table 5, the trapping values improved with increases in grammages. Increases in the physical properties were decreased the trapping values. Otherwise, it was observed that high bulkiness and thickness papers gave better trapping value than others. Gloss coated papers were found to be better than Matt coated papers in terms of the trapping. II. Medium Grade papers gave the best result in this value.

Table 6. The trapping values (%) of the papers

	American Bristol				Coated (115 gsm)				I. High Grade			
	230 gsm		350 gsm		Matt		Gloss		70 gsm		80 gsm	
	C	Y	C	Y	C	Y	C	Y	C	Y	C	Y
+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
M	Y	M	M	Y	M	M	Y	M	M	Y	M	M
74	94	91	75	97	92	73	96	95	76	94	93	74

	II. Medium Grade				III. Low Grade			
	48 gsm		54 gsm		70 gsm		80 gsm	
	C	Y	C	Y	C	Y	C	Y
+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
M	Y	M	M	Y	M	M	Y	M
81	100	98	78	100	97	76	100	95

Table 7. The gamut values of the offset printed papers

	American Bristol		Coated (115 gsm)		I. High Grade		II. Medium Grade		III. Low Grade	
	230 gsm	350 gsm	Matt	Gloss	70 gsm	80 gsm	48 gsm	54 gsm	70 gsm	80 gsm
	Gamut Values	299	322	318	322	172	159	129	159	84

In Table 6, American Bristol and Coated papers gave the best result in the gamut values. The higher the gamut value, the color universe to be obtained in print will be so wide. As the gamut values of other papers were lower, it is stated that the compatibility of these papers with offset printing were less. No result was found that the physical properties indicated had an effect on the gamut values in offset printing.

Table 8. The chroma values of the offset printing papers

Physical Properties	American Bristol		Coated (115 gsm)		I. High Grade		II. Medium Grade		III. Low Grade	
	230 gsm	350 gsm	Matt	Gloss	70 gsm	80 gsm	48 gsm	54 gsm	70 gsm	80 gsm
C	60.59	60.17	60.30	60.33	55.70	56.79	55.45	55.86	52.02	58.87
M	88.70	87.44	88.96	88.96	83.41	83.73	80.40	78.56	73.92	83.73
Y	86.65	85.26	87.69	87.56	85.54	85.95	79.70	77.30	74.81	86.89
K	18.21	16.99	18.67	18.42	25.35	27.63	22.03	22.37	21.78	23.03

Table 9. L, a, and b values of the offset printed papers

	American Bristol			Coated (115 gsm)			I. High Grade											
	230 gsm			350 gsm			Matt			Gloss			70 gsm			80 gsm		
	L	a	b	L	a	b	L	a	b	L	a	b	L	a	b	L	a	b
C	48	-36	-48	49	-36	-47	49	-35	-52	49	-35	-52	49	-25	-49	49	-27	-48
M	49	74	1.9	48	73	1.5	49	74	0.1	49	74	0.1	51	66	1.9	51	66	0.7
Y	87	-2.8	91	85	-1.7	90	88	-4.6	91	87	-4.7	91	86	-1.8	83	86	-2.3	84
K	18	-1.1	5.1	17	-1.1	5.0	19	-1.3	4.2	19	-1.3	4.3	25	-0.7	2.2	28	-0.9	2.8

	II. Medium Grade			III. Low Grade								
	48 gsm			54 gsm			70 gsm			80 gsm		
	L	a	b	L	a	b	L	a	b	L	a	b
C	45	-32	-41	46	-32	-38	43	-29	-29	50	-31	-39
M	46	66	4.8	46	64	4.4	45	59	9.9	53	65	6
Y	79	0.2	81	77	0.2	78	75	1.9	74	87	-0.2	86
K	22	-0.7	4.7	22	-0.6	4.7	22	-0.2	6.8	23	-0.9	5.1

According to all the tables, it is well understood that the physical properties of the papers influence the print quality. The processes required prior to printing must be applied carefully for quality printing process. Paper selection process should take into account which quality parameter and which paper is best suited for offset printing technique.

CONCLUSIONS

This study focuses on the effects of the paper physical properties on the offset printing quality, which provide better paper selection for quality printing. In developed countries, print control strips are used to keep the print quality and to continue same printing quality in graphic, printing, and publishing sectors. The print control strip is a printing element that detecting printing errors in advance and arranging this errors. In addition to the physical properties, the filler and chemicals used in the paper, inks used in printing, the printing machine and employee's psychological condition can also affect the printing quality.

In this study, the print control strips were added to each of the printed papers and evaluated in all the print control parameters. The effects of the physical properties on the offset printing quality were examined and the results were presented in tables and the most appropriate paper type for the offset printing system was determined. Which paper is the most suitable paper according to which offset printing parameters are given below:

Dot gain: II. Medium and III. Low Grade Papers

Print density: III. Low Grade Papers

Print contrast: Coated papers

Trapping: II. Medium Grade Papers

Gamut: Coated and American Bristol Papers

Chroma: Coated and American Bristol Papers

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